

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF CAGE AMINES BY THE RITTER REACTION

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Abstract

The reaction of vinylnorbornene with acetonitrile in the presence of H₂SO₄ at 20 and 50°C was studied. The Ritter reaction for vinylnorbornene with acetonitrile in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid occurs only at the double bond of the ring and leads to 5-vinyl-2(3)-acetaminonorbornane, and in the presence of water in the system - to a significant amount of by-product - 5-vinyl-2(3)-norbornanol. By methods of alkaline hydrolysis and reduction with hydrogen on skeletal nickel and lithium aluminum hydride, 5-vinyl-2(3)-acetaminonorbornane can be converted into the corresponding amines both with and without a double bond in the side chain.

Keywords: cage amines, Ritter reaction, acylated amines, acetonitrile, vinylnorbornene.

It is known that amino derivatives of framework hydrocarbons containing a structural fragment of norbornane exhibit high physiological activity [1]. One of the simplest methods for the synthesis of compounds of this group, for example, acylated amines, is the Ritter reaction, but for bicyclic dienes it has been studied using a small number of examples [2, 3]. In this regard, it was of interest to study the influence of the conditions of this reaction on its direction for vinylnorbornene, which has a high reactivity in addition reactions [4] and is quite accessible [5].

Materials and methods

IR spectra were recorded on a Specord 75-JR instrument, PMR spectra were recorded on Varian Mercury-400 and Bruker Avance DRX 500 spectrometers with TMS in accordance with the internal standard. Chromatographic analysis was carried out on a Tsvet-102 device with a glass column 1000x3 mm (5% Apiezon L on Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier) and a capillary column 50 m long, filled with Apiezon L, carrier gas - helium. Separation of mixtures of reaction products was carried out on Silicagel 40/100 sorbent and TLC on Silufol plates. Freshly distilled technical vinyl norbornene was used for the experiments.

Reaction of vinylnorbornene (1) with acetonitrile.

1. To a solution of 5 g (0.042 mol) of diene (1) in 193.5 ml (3.78 mol) of acetonitrile, 11.5 ml (0.21 mol) of 94% H₂SO₄ and 9 ml (0.5 mol) of water were added with stirring and cooling with ice. Cooling was stopped and kept at 20°C for 24 hours. Then a soda solution was added to the reaction mixture until the reaction was alkaline, the organic layer was separated, and the precipitate was washed with acetonitrile. The combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, and

acetonitrile was removed in vacuo. The residue was analyzed by GLC. Yield of mixture of compounds 6.1 g.

2. Carry out the same procedure as step 1. The reaction mixture was kept for 8 hours at 50°C. Product yield 6.4 g.

3. To a solution of 5 g (0.042 mol) of diene (1) in 193.5 ml (3.78 mol) acetonitrile, 11.5 ml (0.21 mol) of 94% H₂SO₄ was added dropwise over 10 min with stirring and cooling with ice, and left at 20°C for 26 h, then processed as in step 1. Yield of compounds 6.44 g.

5-Vinyl-2(3)-acetylamino norbornane (2). Isolated by column chromatography from a mixture of compounds obtained in step 1, eluent: ether - hexane (10:1). *R_f* 0.5. Yield 0.9 g, mp. 81-88°C. IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 890, 1640, 2900, 3090, 3300. PMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 7.95 br. s (NH, 1H), 5.5 m (-CH=, 1H), 4.75 m (=CH-, 2H), 3.45 m (AcNH-CH=, 1H), 1.2-1.25 (rest H). Found (%): C 73.65, N 9.59, N 7.79. C₁₁H₁₇NO. Calculated (%): C 73.74, N 9.49, N 7.82.

5-Vinyl-2(3)-norbornanol (3). A. Similar to compound (2), *R_f* 0.8 was isolated. Yield 5 g, bp. 75-80°C (1.5 mm Hg) [6]. IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 890, 1640, 2900, 3100, 3310. PMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 5.5 m (-CH=, 1H), 4.75 m (=CH₂, 2H), 3.5 s (OH, 1H), 3.1 m (=CH-OH, 1H), 1.2-2.0 m (rest H). Found (%): C 78.19, H 10.25. Calculated (%): C 78.26, H 10.14.

B. 12 g (0.1 mol) of diene (1) was added to 38 ml of 25% H₂SO₄, cooled with ice and stirred, heated to 95°C and kept for 2 hours. After cooling, extracted with 20 ml of ether, the organic layer was separated, washed with soda solution and dried with anhydrous sulfate sodium. After evaporation of the ether, 13.1 g of residue was obtained with 83% alcohol content (3) (according to GLC data). The mixture was distilled in vacuum, collecting the bp fraction. 85-90°C (1.7 mm Hg) [7], the

alcohol yield was 9.9 g (71.1%). IR spectrum (cm^{-1}): 890, 1640, 2900, 3090, 3305. PMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 5.5 (-CH=, 1H), 4.75 m (=CH₂, 2H), 3.5 br. s (OH, 1H), 3.0 m (=CH-OH, 1H), 1.2-2.0 m (rest H).

Reaction of 5-vinyl-2(3)-norbornanol (3) with acetonitrile.

To a solution of 15 g of alcohol (3), obtained by the Ritter reaction from diene (2), in 5.8 ml of acetonitrile, 0.35 ml of 94% H₂SO₄ and 0.25 ml of water were added. Reaction. the mass was kept for 1 hour at 50-60°C, then treated with a soda solution and the organic layer was separated. The sodium sulfate precipitate was washed with acetonitrile and the combined extracts were dried over Na₂SO₄. After distilling off the solvent, 0.2 g of a mixture was obtained, which contained 67% alcohol (3) and 33% acetamine derivative (2) (according to GLC).

5-Vinyl-2(3)-aminonorbornane (4). To a solution of 3 g of acetamine (2) in 35 ml of diethylene glycol, 4.68 g of KOH was added and boiled for 6 hours.

After cooling, the mixture was poured into 200 ml of 10% KOH and extracted with ether. The extract was dried over KOH. Dry HCl gas was passed through the ethereal solution. The precipitate that formed was filtered off. The yield of hydrochloride was 2.19 g (76%). The action of a 10% KOH solution isolated free amine (4) in the form of a viscous dark liquid. PMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 5.5 m (-CH=, 1H), 4.75 m (=CH₂, 2H), 2.75 m (-CH-NH₂, 1H), 1.2-2.0 (rest H). Found (%): C 78.73, N 11.05, N 10/19. C₉H₁₅N. Calculated (%): C 78.83, N 10.95, N 10.22.

5-Ethyl-2(3)-aminonorbornane (5). A suspension of Ni-Raney in methanol was added to a solution of 0.5 g of amine hydrochloride (4) in 30 ml of methanol. The mixture was stirred for 6 hours at 20°C in a hydrogen atmosphere. Methanol and catalyst were removed. We obtained 0.5 g of amine hydrochloride (5). NMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 8.0 (-NH₃⁺, 3H), 3/0 (-CH-NH₃⁺, 1H), 1.5-2.5 (rest H). Amine (5) was isolated, like amine (4), in the form of an oily liquid with n_D^{20} 1.4677 [9].

5-Ethyl-2(3)-acylamino norbornane (6). A suspension of Ni-Raney in methanol was added to a solution of 1.0 g of compound (2) in 30 ml of methanol. The mixture was stirred for 6 hours at 20°C in a hydrogen atmosphere. The catalyst and solvent were removed. The yield of compound (6) in the form of a viscous liquid was 1.0 g. PIR spectrum (δ , ppm): 5.75 (NH, 1H), 3.5 (-CH-NH-COCH₃, 1H), 1.6 (-COCH₃, 3H), 0.6-2.1 (rest H). Found (%): S 72.86, N 10.50, N 7.75. C₁₁H₁₉NO. Calculated (%): C 72.93, N 10.50, N 7.73.

5-Ethyl-2(3)-acetamino-norbornane (7). To a suspension of 0.4 g of LiAlH₄ in 50 ml of ether, 0.9 g of compound (6) was added, heated to boiling and stirred for 4 hours. After cooling, 1.6 ml of water and 0.4 ml of 15% NaOH were successively added, and the precipitate was filtered off inorganic salts. The filtrate was dried over KOH and ether saturated with HCl was added. The precipitate was filtered off. The yield of amine hydrochloride (7) was 0.9 g (91%), m.p. 190-193°C. Amine (7) was isolated, like amine (4), n_D^{20} 1.4820 [9]. Found (%): C 78.93, N 12.67, N 8.83. C₁₁H₂₁N. Calculated (%): C 79.04, N 12.57, N 8.38.

5-Vinyl-2(3)-N-ethylaminonorbornane (8). 1.0 g of acetamine (2) was added to a suspension of 0.4 g of lithium aluminum hydride in 50 ml of ether. Stir for 8 hours at boiling until the precipitate disappears. The mixture was treated as for compound (7). The yield of amine hydrochloride (8) was 1.05 g (93%). Free amine (8) was obtained in the form of a viscous liquid, as was amine (4). Found (%): S 79.91, N 11.63, N 8.45. C₁₁H₁₉N. Calculated (%): C 80.00, N 11.52, N 8.48.

Results and discussion

This paper presents the results of a study of the interaction of vinylnorbornene (1) with acetonitrile in the presence of sulfuric acid, which, as experiments have shown, occurs with the formation of the following products:

The reaction was carried out at different molar ratios of the reagents, sulfuric acid and water, changing the time and temperature of the experiments (see Table 1). For the experiments we used H₂SO₄ conc. and excess acetonitrile, since it was used as a reagent and sol-

vent at the same time. Application of H₂SO₄ conc. allows you to increase the proportion of protonated nitrile and, accordingly, reduce the solvation of carbocations formed during the protonation of vinylnorbornene, which increases their reactivity [2].

Table 1.

Composition of the reaction products of vinylnorbornene (1) with acetonitrile (according to GLC)				
# exp.	Mole ratio (1):MeCN:H ₂ O:H ₂ SO ₄	τ, h	T, °C	Yield, %
1	1:90:12:5	26	20	15(2), 82(3)
2	1:90:12:5	8	50	59(2), 41(3)
3	1:90:0:5	26	20	86(2)

In some experiments, water was added to the reaction medium in order to prevent various rearrangements of these carbocations [2, 6]. However, it turned out that this leads not only to the formation of the target reaction product - 5-vinyl-2(3)-acetylamino-norbornane (2), but also to a significant amount of 5-vinyl-2(3)-norbornanol (3). The formation of alcohol (3) was confirmed by experiment, in which by adding olefin (1) to 25% H₂SO₄ at 95°C for only 2 hours, alcohol (3) was obtained with a yield of 83%. As can be seen from the table data, a noticeable increase the amount of the main product (2), even in the presence of water, is promoted by an increase in temperature while simultaneously reducing the reaction time. Probably, in this case, the main role in shifting the process towards the formation of acetamine derivative (2) is played by an increase in temperature, since the alcohol itself (3) when interacting with acetonitrile in the presence of sulfuric acid and water at 50-60°C in 1 hour is converted into compound (2) with a yield of 33%.

The composition of the reaction products was studied by GLC. When analyzing the preparatively isolated acetamino derivative (2) and alcohol (3) on a ca-

pillary column, two peaks are visible in the chromatograms in a 1:1 ratio. The IR spectra of these compounds contain absorption bands at 890, 1640 and 2900 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the terminal vinyl group, the presence of which is confirmed by proton signals at 4.75 (=CH₂) and 5.5 (-CH=) ppm. in PMR spectra. The stretching vibrations of the NH group of compound (2) are characterized by an absorption band in the IR spectrum at 3300 cm⁻¹, absorption of the OH group of alcohol (3) - at 3100, 3310 cm⁻¹. The NMR spectra of these compounds contain broadened singlets of the NH group proton at 7.95 ppm and the hydroxyl proton at 3.5 ppm. Among the multiplet signals of the protons of the norbornane fragment, one can distinguish multiplets of methine protons at C2, C3 atoms with centers for acetamine (2) at 3.45 and alcohol (3) at 3.1 ppm. The ranges of chemical shifts of the remaining protons correspond to literature data [7, 8] From the given spectral data and GLC results it follows that under the studied conditions the reaction proceeds through an endocyclic double bond with the formation of 2-3-substituted isomers of 5-vinylnorbornane. Possible transformations of the synthesized acetamine (2) into other amines of the norbornane series are shown in the diagram:

Alkaline hydrolysis of compound (2) yielded 5-vinyl-2(3)-aminonorbornane (4), and hydrogenation on Ni-Raney yielded 5-ethyl-2(3)-aminonorbornane (5). Sequential reduction with hydrogen on Ni-Raney and LiAlH₄ yielded 5-ethyl-2(3)-acetylamino-norbornane (6) and 5-ethyl-2(3)-N-ethylaminonorbornane (7). By reducing LiAlH₄ from compound (2), 5-vinyl-2(3)-ethylaminonorbornane (8) was obtained.

Conclusions

1. The Ritter reaction for vinylnorbornene with acetonitrile in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid occurs only at the double bond of the ring and leads to

5-vinyl-2(3)-acetaminonorbornane, and in the presence of water in the system - to a significant amount of by-product - 5-vinyl-2(3)-norbornanol.

2. By methods of alkaline hydrolysis and reduction with hydrogen on skeletal nickel and lithium aluminum hydride, 5-vinyl-2(3)-acetaminonorbornane can be converted into the corresponding amines both with and without a double bond in the side chain.

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